

WARM UP ACTIVITIES IN LANGUAGE CLASSROOM

Sapaeva Ugiljon Bakhtiyor kizi

English teacher of school No. 9 in Urgench district of Khorezm region

Eshchanov Jasur Matkarimovich

English teacher of school No. 9 in Urgench district of Khorezm region

Annotation: Sometimes it is difficult for teachers to attract students' attention and lead them into the world of English as they are either hectic or exhausted or may be tired or hungry. As for the teachers they try to develop students' reading, writing, speaking and listening skills as well as the vocabulary and structure at the same time. Teachers want to inspire, to motivate their students and to create a mood for learning, growth, and communication in the classroom and they always seek activities that could maintain their students be active learners as well as creative during the lessons. Using warm-up activities in the classroom is a good way to help teachers to deal with such obstacles.

Keywords: motivate, facilitated, learning, fun, benefits, relationship, focus attention

INTRODUCTION

Learning process is facilitated through building a positive relationship with the students. As Krishnan and Hoon stated, a fun or interesting class largely depends on the teachers as their personality and teaching method motivate the students to raise a positive attitude towards learning. Warm-up activities are essential in the English classroom. Students may be tired or have other things on their minds and diving straight into a textbook or grammar explanation can be quite jarring. With a good warmer we can put our students into English mode;

attentive, interested and ready to participate. A warmer can also serve to review language from a previous lesson or prime the class for a new topic¹.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Warm up activities are suggested to be used to maintain all skills of learners for English as a foreign language. Gathering the attention of students and getting them participate in such practices may turn into a challenge for English instructors. As for me, I mostly attempt to use warm-up activities to engage my students into the topic and raise their interest in learning more about the theme within my classroom. Modern teaching is characterized by interaction, communication and participation. It is believed that an interactive class must incorporate participation in order to assure learner centered teaching and better results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A warm up activity is a short, fun game which a teacher or trainer can use with students. The purpose of a warm up is to:

- encourage the students
- wake them up – first thing in the morning and after lunch people are often a little sleepy
- prepare them to learn by stimulating their minds and/or their bodies.

Warm ups should last about 5 minutes. Warm ups are particularly useful²:

- to help new students or trainees to get to know each other
- to mark the shift when students have finished learning about one topic before starting on a new topic. I consider warm up activities are essential teaching techniques for good teacher and trainers as they help students to get to know each other. It is good and advisable to use warm up activities at the

¹Robertson, C., & Acklam, R. (2010). Action Plan for Teachers a guide to teaching English. London, UK: BBC World Service.

² Velandia, R. (2018). The Role of Warming Up Activities in Adolescent Students' Involvement During the English Class. Profile Journal, 10, 9-26

beginning of the lesson. Activities at the start of the lesson deserve more attention than they usually receive. In fact, the initial activities that start the class are very important for the following reasons:

1: Warm Ups set the tone of the lesson. For example, an activity that students find too difficult or confusing can prove discouraging.

2: Warm Ups get students to begin thinking and focusing on English. It may have been a few days, a week, or even longer since they last used English. A little time here will improve receptivity later.

3: Warm Ups provide a transition into the topic. An activity at the start of the lesson activates pre-existing knowledge on a subject, and may even get students to use (or consider) some of the ideas, vocabulary, or even grammar important to the lesson.

4: Warm Ups allow the teacher important opportunities to assess character and ability. After all, some students work well together, and others don't. Some students have good days, and others bad. During the initial activity, the teacher can determine who will form the best groups for subsequent activities.

Proverb matching

It is a warm up activity in which every student gets a half proverb card and has to find out his\her partner for the other half. They together have to come up with a story or situation which illustrates their proverb and others can guess the proverb.

Superlative Speaking Cards³

This is a fun follow-up speaking activity for practicing superlatives. There are 24 cards. Cut them and give one to each student. They should

³ Cheung, C. K. (2011). The use of popular culture as a stimulus to motivate secondary students' English learning in Hong Kong. *ELT Journal*, 55 (1), 55-61.

answer the question: 'Who's the ... student in the class?' following the format: I think/believe/hold that the ... student in the class is

..., because he/she

What do you know about bananas?

Set a five-minute time limit and in groups have students think up and write down as many facts as they can about bananas (or cats, Belgium, David Beckham, etc.). One point should be given for each true sentence.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, to start a class with an interesting activity, to help the students set a positive mood for learning and to keep them engaged in class, using warmup activity can be an effective way. It is obvious that, in a language classroom warm up activity can be used for many reasons. One of the reasons of using warm up is to establish a good relationship between students and teachers and to set a positive learning environment for the students to make them comfortable in classroom. Then, warm up can be used to motivate the students so that they become interested to learn. Moreover, teachers can use warm up to get students' attention at the beginning of the class. Also, the use of warm up also can be a good exercise for the students to recall their background knowledge. As well as, teachers can discuss the lesson objectives in the warm up session so that students get a clear goal to give higher effort to learn. It is necessary to tell the students why they are doing certain tasks. A warm up session can be a good time to discuss the lesson objective so that students get a valid reason to perform any activity.

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